

OVERLOADING PROBLEM OF THE MAIN ELECTRICAL NETWORK OF THE MULTI-APARTMENT BUILDINGS AFTER POWER SUPPLY RESTORATION FOLLOWING A PROLONGED POWER CUT

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Abstract

At present frequent and prolonged power cuts of electricity consumers are a unique phenomenon in the electrical networks of technologically advanced power systems. At the same time, such power cuts have been occurring in Ukraine since 2022 and continue to this day. The causes of these power cuts are the destructive effects of military action on electricity infrastructure, both in terms of generation and the transmission and distribution of electricity.

The deficit of active power generation in Ukraine's Interconnected Power System (IPS) necessitates the forced disconnection of some consumers in order to maintain the active power balance and keep the voltage frequency at 50 Hz. Given the significant duration of periods with a deficit in active power generation, scheduled power cut-off schedules were introduced in Ukraine to meet the basic electricity needs of the people, under which each group of consumers has electricity supply during specific time slots throughout the day. At the same time, the people's adaptation to these power cut schedules and the specific operating patterns of certain groups of domestic electrical appliances have led to the problem of overloading the main electrical wiring in multi-apartment buildings. This phenomenon is common for all densely populated cities in the country and creates the conditions for a very large number of faults to occur simultaneously in the main electrical networks of such buildings.

In this article the author sets out his view on the causes of this problem and possible ways of addressing it.

Keywords: multi-apartment building, main electrical network overloading, power cut, power supply restoration.

Introduction

Since 2022 the people of Ukraine has been facing frequent and prolonged power cuts caused by damage to power stations, substations and power transmission lines resulting from military destruction. The deficit in electricity generation within Ukraine's IPS has necessitated the implementation of mechanisms to forcibly restrict consumption in order to maintain the balance of active power and to keep voltage frequency at 50 Hz. For this purpose, six rounds of power cuts were established in the IPS of Ukraine, comprising two sub-rounds each, with a total scheduled load of approximately 6000 MW. Based on these, scheduled power cut timetables were introduced, under which each group of consumers receives electricity only during specific time slots throughout the day.

The total daily duration of periods with electricity supply during the winter of 2025–2026 was often reduced to 2...3 hours, which created significant problems in ensuring the normal daily life and activities of the population.

In order to provide a normal way of life during power cuts, the Ukrainian people has begun actively implementing projects aimed at achieving energy self-sufficiency for households. For private households such projects involved the installation of petrol or diesel generators and low-power (up to 10 kW) solar power stations with hybrid inverters and storage batteries. For flats in multi-storey buildings such projects involved the installation of charging stations or grid-connected inverters with storage batteries.

According to data from the World Integrated Trade Solution portal import into Ukraine of static converters, which include inverters, amounted to \$115,1 million in 2022, \$200,5 million in 2023, and \$362,9

million in 2024 [1]. This allows us to estimate the total number of imported devices at approximately 400 000 ... 500 000 units. Given the growth trend in imports of static converters, it can be stated that a total of 650 000 ... 750 000 devices were imported into Ukraine during the period 2022–2025. Taking into account the proportion of inverters in the total volume of imported static converters and the distribution of urban and rural populations in Ukraine, it can be stated that at least 300 000 inverters with a rated power of up to 6 kW are currently being used in conjunction with storage batteries to provide backup power supply to flats in multi-storey buildings. The number of charging stations with a capacity of up to 5 kWh and a charging power of up to 3.5 kW used in flats in such buildings can be estimated at approximately the same figure.

During power cuts from the external grid as part of scheduled power cuts the batteries connected to the hybrid inverters and charging stations batteries gradually discharge supplying electricity to consumers. Once power supply from the external grid is restored hybrid inverters and charging stations switch to battery charging mode adding the charging power to the power consumption of other household appliances. Given the charging power of typical domestic charging stations and domestic inverters in the initial moments after the restoration of power supply from the external grid situations arise in the main electrical networks of multi-apartment buildings where power is transmitted in excess of design capacity, which leads to the emergency shutdown of such networks due to the tripping of a fuse or circuit breaker, which will result in the interruption of the power supply to all consumers on that network.

Analysis of the causes of emergency power cuts in the main electrical networks of apartment buildings following the restoration of power supply

Typical designs for apartment buildings in Ukraine's major cities include 5-storey, 9-storey and 16-storey residential buildings.

Figure 1 – Power supply diagram for the flats on a floor of a typical 9-storey building

For 16-storey buildings the design specification for the energy source used for cooking is electricity; therefore the contracted electrical capacity for a flat in such a building is 10 kW (single phase). There are usually 6 or 7 flats per floor in such buildings. For a building with 6 flats per floor power is supplied via two main lines; for building with 7 flats per floor power is supplied via three main lines.

Therefore, the maximum load on the main supply line will be 12 flats with a contracted power of 5 kW per phase for a typical 9-storey building, and 16 flats with a contracted power of 10 kW per phase for a typical 16-storey building.

For typical 9-storey buildings the cross-section of the main aluminium busbar is 50...70 mm² with a permissible current of 165...210 A; for typical 16-storey buildings the cross-section of the main aluminium busbar is 120...150 mm² with a permissible current of 300...355 A [2].

In condition of the a stable power supply from the external grid the total load from the flats on each phase of the main line $P_{ph\ fl}$ can be calculated as follows [3]:

$$P_{ph\ fl} = P_0 \cdot N, \quad (1)$$

where:

P_0 – the estimated specific electrical load per dwelling (flat), which is determined using a table based on the assumed level of electrification and the number of flats connected to that section of the electricity network;

N – the number of dwellings (flats) connected to the line.

For 9-storey buildings the design specification for the energy source used for cooking is natural gas; therefore the contracted electrical connection capacity for each flat in such a building is 5 kW (single phase). There are usually 4 or 6 flats per floor in such buildings. For a building with 4 flats per floor power is supplied via single main line (Fig. 1a); for building with 6 flats per floor power is supplied via two main lines (Fig. 1b).

According to Table 6.1 [3] for a typical 9-storey building $P_0 = 2,36$ kW and for a typical 16-storey building $P_0 = 3,05$ kW, therefore total load from the flats on each phase of the main line according (1):

$$P_{ph\ fl}^9 = 2,36 \cdot 12 = 28,32 \text{ kW};$$

$$P_{ph\ fl}^{12} = 3,24 \cdot 16 = 51,84 \text{ kW}.$$

The phase current in the main line, caused by the load from the flats, can be determined as:

$$I_{ph\ fl} = \frac{P_{ph\ fl}}{U_{nom} \cdot \cos\varphi}, \quad (2)$$

where:

U_{nom} – nominal voltage of the main line of the building (for Ukraine $U_{nom} = 230$ V);

$\cos\varphi$ – power factor for flat by the Table 6.5 [3] (for a typical 9-storey building $\cos\varphi = 0,96$, for a typical 16-storey building $\cos\varphi = 0,98$).

Thus the phase currents in the main line for the typical buildings:

$$I_{ph\ fl}^9 = \frac{28,32}{0,23 \cdot 0,96} = 128,3 \text{ A};$$

$$I_{ph\ fl}^{16} = \frac{51,84}{0,23 \cdot 0,98} = 230,0 \text{ A}.$$

An analysis of the results shows that in condition of the stable electricity supply the main circuits in typical buildings are not overloaded.

If the power supply is restored following a prolonged outage, the power required to charge the battery of a hybrid inverter or charging station is added to the typical loads; the presence of such equipment in flats is not provided for in the standard [3].

In this case, the total load from the flats on each phase of the main line will be:

$$P_{ph\ fl} = (P_0 + P_{ch} \cdot k_d) \cdot N, \quad (3)$$

where:

P_{ch} – charging active power of the charging station or the hybrid inverter;

k_d – share of apartments with installed charging stations or hybrid inverters.

For charging stations the typical charging power is 1,5...3,5 kW, for single-phase hybrid inverters – 3,5...6,0 kW. The results of the calculation of the total

load per phase on the main line from the flats and the phase current of the main line for different charging powers of the charging station and inverter, for different proportions of flats with installed charging stations or hybrid inverters for typical 9-floor and 16-floor buildings are shown in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1

Total load per phase and phase current of the main line from the flats of the typical 9-floor building

P_{ch} , kW	$P_{ph,fl}$, kW / $I_{ph,fl}$, A				
	$k_d=10\%$	$k_d=20\%$	$k_d=30\%$	$k_d=40\%$	$k_d=50\%$
1,5	30,1 / 136,4	31,9 / 144,6	33,7 / 152,7	35,5 / 160,1	37,3 / 169,0
3,0	31,9 / 144,6	35,5 / 160,9	39,1 / 177,2	42,7 / 193,5	46,3 / 209,8
4,5	33,7 / 152,7	39,1 / 177,2	44,5 / 201,6	49,9 / 226,1	55,3 / 250,5
6,0	35,5 / 160,9	42,7 / 193,5	49,9 / 226,1	57,1 / 258,7	64,3 / 291,3

Table 2

Total load per phase and phase current of the main line from the flats of the typical 16-floor building

P_{ch} , kW	$P_{ph,fl}$, kW / $I_{ph,fl}$, A				
	$k_d=10\%$	$k_d=20\%$	$k_d=30\%$	$k_d=40\%$	$k_d=50\%$
1,5	54,2 / 240,6	56,6 / 251,3	59,0 / 261,9	61,4 / 272,6	63,8 / 283,2
3,0	56,6 / 251,3	61,5 / 272,6	66,2 / 293,9	71,0 / 315,2	75,8 / 336,5
4,5	59,0 / 261,9	66,2 / 293,9	73,4 / 325,8	80,6 / 357,8	87,8 / 389,7
6,0	61,4 / 272,6	71,0 / 315,2	80,6 / 357,8	90,2 / 400,4	99,8 / 442,9

In Table 1 and Table 2 yellow color indicates that the permissible current has been exceeded on the main supply line with a cross-section of 50 mm² for a typical 9-storey building and 120 mm² for a typical 16-storey building, red color indicates an exceedance of the permissible current in the main line with a cross-section of 70 mm² for a typical 9-storey building and 150 mm² for a typical 16-storey building.

An analysis of Table 1 and Table 2 shows that problem with overloading of the main distribution lines in apartment buildings arise even when hybrid inverters with a charging capacity of 4,5 kW or higher are installed in 20% of the flats in the building, and charging stations with a charging capacity of 1,5 kW – for 50% of the flats in the building. Given the previously cited data on the number of inverters and charging stations imported into Ukraine, the results obtained indicate the risk of widespread incidents involving the disconnection of main power lines in apartment buildings and power cuts to consumers.

Recommendations for preventing emergency power cuts to the main lines of apartment buildings following the restoration of the electricity supply

In order to prevent emergency power cuts on the main supply lines of apartment buildings the author recommends implementing the following measures:

1) Inform the public of the need to avoid situations where charging stations or hybrid inverters are operating in charging mode alongside other high-power electrical appliances (electric hobs, boilers, heaters, irons, etc.).

2) Recommend that manufacturers importing charging stations and hybrid inverters into the country reduce the charging current in the factory settings to half of the maximum permissible value.

3) Recommend that energy supply companies install smart meters with the ability to remotely change settings and limit electricity consumption, which will enable them to temporarily disconnect consumers whose electricity consumption exceeds a certain limit.

Conclusions

It has been established that the main cause of emergency power cuts to the main supply lines of apartment buildings in Ukrainian cities following the restoration of power from the external grid is currently the widespread use by the public of charging stations and hybrid inverters with rechargeable batteries, the charging mode of which is characterised by high power consumption. With a view to reducing the number of such outages the author recommends the implementation of a series of preventive measures.

References

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